

ENRICHING THE VOCABULARY OF SENIOR SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. This article examines the enrichment of senior schoolchildren's vocabulary in foreign language lessons. By implementing the tasks of enriching schoolchildren's speech, a language teacher forms their evaluative attitude to the selection (choice) of language means depending on a set of factors such as the task, addressee, time, place of utterance, etc.

Key words: vocabulary, methods, foreign language, level, written and oral speech.

Formation of good speech is a special aspect of work on the culture of speech of students. This direction is reflected in the current programs. At the same time, in the programs - with regard to large topics - the following are designated mainly: synonymous series (less often - antonymous pairs of words) of nouns, adjectives, verbs, adverbs, etc.; parallel syntactic constructions; the sphere of use of individual morphological categories, word forms, syntactic constructions, etc.

Thus, enrichment of students' speech presupposes their awareness of the shades of lexical and grammatical meanings of words, word forms, constructions, as well as their stylistic features, sphere of use. This understanding is the basis on which the teaching of the choice (from what is available in the speech memory) of the optimal linguistic means for a certain speech situation is built.

In the domestic methodology in terms of enriching the speech of schoolchildren, the following are distinguished: vocabulary work; work on enriching the grammatical (including intonation) structure of the speech of students. Enriching the vocabulary of students is the most important task of the school course of a foreign language. The need for special work on enriching the vocabulary of students is determined, firstly, by the extremely important role of the word in the language (being the central unit of language, it carries a variety of semantic information - conceptual, emotive, functional-stylistic and grammatical; filling certain positions in communicative units - sentences, the word ensures acts of speech communication between people), and secondly, by the need for constant replenishment of the vocabulary (the more words a person knows, the more accurately communication between people is realized both orally and in writing).

The need to expand the vocabulary of students is determined by various reasons. The surrounding life, studying at school, reading books, newspapers, magazines, listening to radio and television programs enrich the knowledge of schoolchildren, along with which they often come to know unfamiliar words. Assimilation of knowledge in this case involves memorizing new words. Possession of a large stock of words provides the student with a better understanding of what is read, free, without difficulties, communication in different groups of people. The desire of senior schoolchildren to expand their vocabulary in foreign language lessons should be supported by the school. Words are used differently in functional and stylistic varieties of language, which is associated with the features of their primary and additional lexical meanings. Understanding this connection by schoolchildren is the basis for teaching schoolchildren the ability to use known and new words in their own statements, stylistically differentiated.

Quantitative expansion of the vocabulary of students is expressed in the gradual addition of new words to the existing words (the level of replenishment of lexemes in a foreign language). Qualitative improvement of vocabulary consists, firstly, in clarifying the lexical meaning and scope of use of words known to schoolchildren, and secondly, in replacing non-literary words in the vocabulary of students with literary ones (the level of language improvement). Finally, a special aspect of the quantitative and qualitative improvement of the vocabulary of schoolchildren is the work on familiarization with the lexical meanings of polysynaptic words already in their vocabulary (the level of proficiency in a foreign language). The difference between the active part of a student's personal vocabulary and its passive part is the level of proficiency in the word. To own a word means to correlate it with reality or concept, to know its semantics, compatibility and scope of use. If in the student's mind a word has all of the above-mentioned features, then it is included in the active part of his personal vocabulary. If a word in his mind is related to a reality or concept and he understands it at least in the most general form, then such a word is included in the passive part of his personal vocabulary. The probability of its use in the speech of a schoolchild is small. The function of these words in the personal vocabulary is to ensure understanding of what is read or heard. In the initial teaching of a foreign language, the boundaries between the passive and active parts of the personal vocabulary of a schoolchild are quite flexible: the active vocabulary increases due to both new words and the transition of words from the passive to the active part of the personal vocabulary. The task of a foreign language teacher is to help students master the combinability and scope of application of passive words in order to transfer them to the active vocabulary of the student, i.e. to solve both problems of enriching the vocabulary of the student and to help raise the level of language proficiency.

The listed sources (or ways) of replenishing the vocabulary of senior school students in foreign language lessons, depending on how they are perceived by students - visually or aurally, make up the following groups: perceived visually (reading books, textbooks, newspapers and magazines); perceived aurally (speech of the teacher, peers, adults, listening to the radio, watching TV programs, movies, theatrical performances); perceived simultaneously visually and aurally (watching filmstrips, special film fragments with subtitles, visiting museums, exhibitions).

According to the degree of teacher influence on the specified ways of replenishing the vocabulary of students, they are divided into controlled and partially controlled. Controlled ways of replenishing the vocabulary of senior school students include the school lexical minimum of the foreign language studied at school, and the educational speech of the teacher himself. In his/her educational speech, the teacher purposefully selects the necessary vocabulary, "presents" it with the expectation that schoolchildren will learn the lexical meanings of words, and includes these words in appropriate contexts to demonstrate their use. The teacher, where necessary, returns to what was said earlier, varying his/her educational speech. In the course of explanation, he/she can obtain information about the degree to which senior schoolchildren have learned new words and restructure his/her presentation. With the help of textbooks on the foreign language being studied at school, schoolchildren learn words and terms corresponding to their level of proficiency in a certain system established by their authors. One of the tasks is the purposeful quantitative and qualitative improvement of senior schoolchildren's vocabulary, teaching them the ability to use their personal vocabulary.

Partially controlled sources of replenishing students' vocabulary include reading, listening to the radio, watching TV programs, movies, etc. in a foreign language, communicating with adults and peers (the level of proficiency in a foreign language is much higher than theirs). Guidance in enriching students' vocabulary based on these sources is indirect: a foreign language teacher can influence primarily not the acquisition of words, but the acquisition of content. The following tips from a teacher organizing students' activities contribute most to enriching the vocabulary: 1) while reading books in a foreign language, listening to radio and television programs, watching movies, plays, visiting museums, exhibitions, write down new unfamiliar words in dictionaries; 2) later find out the meanings and usage of these words in dictionaries and from the teacher; 3) use them in foreign language lessons in your speech. The foreign language teacher periodically gets acquainted with the students' notes, compiling on this basis thematic vocabularies for working on them both in class and in additional classes.

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